

Project¹ Number: 101086293

Project Acronym: CRISPIt

Project title: Bridging fundamental knowledge and novel technology
to increase rice heat tolerance

DISSEMINATION PLAN

¹ The term 'project' used in this template equates to an 'action' in certain other Horizon 2020 documentation

Plan for the dissemination & exploitation activities

The CRIS Pit consortium will guarantee the dissemination of the results produced. CRIS Pit has highly experienced partner organisations that will be included in the overall exchanges of staff members, thus new and interesting solutions will be developed, from the beginning of the programme, to disseminate the research results.

Results will be made available to the scientific community by **publishing in quality peer-reviewed open-access scientific journals** and will be presented at **national and international scientific conferences and meetings**. Furthermore, international **workshops, meetings** and **training courses** will be organised and will be open to non-participant scientists and students from consortium organisations, therefore enhancing interactions and disseminating our results to scientific and industrial target groups and stakeholders. Where appropriate, **CRIS Pit** will communicate research progress and achievements to the **local press** through the appropriate **Public Relations Offices** at each participating institution. This will constitute an important contribution to the public discussion of science in general and plant biotechnology in particular.

An important product of CRIS Pit project is training exchange. The interdisciplinary research programme is specifically suitable for the state-of-the-art training and career development staff members, in the field of plant molecular methodologies, to identify and characterise genes, and signalling pathways involved in the different reproductive tissues during the double fertilization process in favourable control and under heat stress conditions. Accomplishment of reproductive development leads to the productions of seeds, which is critically important and the primary basis for human sustenance. Therefore, **interactions with public and private sector stakeholders** (i.e., agriculture farmers, small and large seed companies, and research institutions) involved worldwide in the production, distribution and marketing of seeds are expected. Regional, national and European stakeholders, such as seed companies, farmers and farmers consortia and regulators, will be informed through small conferences of the promising use of the genetic materials developed/tested in the project.

There is a clear communication and public engagements strategy in **CRIS Pit**, based on the learn-teach-create training concept, developing the staff member's skills to this task, with the important help of our partner organisations. Internally, the communication will lay down a collaborative working platform, serving the joint work on project implementation and management, reports and publications and also for adopting common good practices. Instant messaging tools, already in use by the team, will also facilitate and promote the fast communication of the consortium and involve all the staff members. The skills and creations produced together

with the partner organisations, during the Staff Exchanges activities and its workshops, will be presented on a dedicated public website designed and created by the consortium (<https://www.fc.up.pt/crispit/>), newsletters, other online platforms and frequently used professional and social networks from our laboratories (<https://twitter.com/spredlab>; <https://www.instagram.com/spredlab/>). This will present the **CRISpit** project and developed work to the wider audience, in a way that we can reach out society showing the benefits of our research.

The development of ground-breaking improvements to improve crops development, will be enhanced by making the data available to the scientific community, companies with interests in the area and the public in general. This latter target is imperative because public interaction is critical to ensure the world better accepts the new research and knowledge developed. For this we also intend to contribute to a shift in thinking in the main world leaders and population, by disseminating our knowledge and making it accessible for the public to better understand how genetically modified crops/edited crops can improve crop yield and help to sustain the world's growing population. The knowledge about how reproductive plant tissues cope with heat stress will provide valuable information about plant sexual reproduction resilience. The knowledge acquired will help to design tailored strategies for an improved seed production in adverse environmental conditions. Research activities as well as results obtained will be made known to society at large in a way that they can be understood by non-specialists, thereby improving the public's understanding of science. This will be done broadcasting written communicates in a way general public could understand and appreciate how the discover of pathways related to resistant to heat stress could revolutionize agriculture. The interaction with the public will also help researchers to better understand public interest in priorities for science and technology and the general public concerns. To make the public in general understand the benefits of this we intend to share our knowledge by participating in local public events such as the **Researchers' Night, the Fascination of Plants Day**, organised by EPSO (EPSO, the European Plant Science Organisation). Events organised by UPORTO such as "**Mostra da Universidade do Porto**", where scientific knowledge is shared with the general public, and **IJUP** (Encontro Investigação Jovem da Universidade do Porto) where scientific knowledge is shared between members of the University. In Milan, Italy, we will attend "**Meet me Tonight**" (<http://www.meetmetonight.it/>) and **exhibitions** (as Botanical gardens open days). Scientific events will also be organized by the URN in the frame of the research network federation "**Normandie-Végétal**" that usually brings together more than 150 scientists from France and other International/European countries. In addition, a national event "**Fêtes de la Science**" is organized annually in which we will also communicate about the project to general public.

The communication of the project progress, supervised by the Coordinator, will make use of the Project Participant Portal, also to facilitate the internal communication between the partner institutions.